

Phytochemical, Proximate, Vitamins and Minerals Composition of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves

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ABSTRACT

Ocimum gratissimum also known as Africa basil/sweet basil is widely found in tropical and subtropical regions and is commonly used as food spice and traditional herb in the treatment of a variety of ailments. The current study therefore evaluated the chemical constituents: proximate (crude fiber, ash, fat and protein), phytochemicals (flavonoids, tannins, saponins, polyphenols, alkaloids and hydrocyanide), mineral elements (Mn, Se, Zn, Fe, Cu, Mg, Cr) and vitamins (A, C, E, riboflavin, niacin and thiamine) using standard methods. Results are as follows proximate ($4.2 \pm 0.32\%$, $1.15 \pm 0.05\%$, $2.7 \pm 0.05\%$ and $4.43 \pm 0.19\%$ for crude fiber, ash, fat and protein respectively); phytochemicals ($1.93 \pm 0.09\%$, $0.56 \pm 0.04\%$, $1.06 \pm 0.03\%$, $0.47 \pm 0.02\%$, $0.41 \pm 0.01\%$ and $0.00 \pm 0.00\%$ for flavonoids, tannins, saponins, polyphenols, alkaloids and hydrocyanide respectively); mineral elements (0.002 ± 0.02 mg/100g, 0.36 ± 0.07 mg/100g, 0.004 ± 0.89 mg/100g, 7.03 ± 0.19 mg/100g, 0.01 ± 0.12 mg/100g and 0.06 ± 0.58 mg/100g and nil for Mn, Se, Zn, Fe, Cu, Mg, Cr respectively) and vitamins (1402.33 ± 5.89 IU/100g, 0.0025 ± 0.36 mg/100g, 19.33 ± 0.88 mg/100g, $7.8 \pm 0.06\%$, $4.11 \pm 0.11\%$ and $23.33 \pm 1.2\%$ for vitamins A, C, E, riboflavin, niacin and thiamine respectively). The findings from this work shows that *Ocimum gratissimum* may be a good source of medically active phytochemicals and micronutrients necessary in health and disease. Thus, justifying its use traditionally in the treatment of ailments.

Keywords: *Ocimum gratissimum*, phytochemicals, micronutrient, vitamins

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have contributed immensely to health care in various continents and are known to play important roles as source of food, maintenance of good health and treatment of diseases [1]. This is due in part to the recognition of the value of traditional medical systems, particularly in Asian origin, and the identification of medicinal plant from indigenous pharmacopoeias and traditional knowledge.

Ocimum gratissimum also known as Africa basil/sweet basil, is a plant belonging to Lamiceae family. It has been used for centuries as folk medicine. It is known as a food spice and traditional herb, which has been recommended for the treatment of various diseases [2, 3]. In traditional systems of medicine, many herbs including *Ocimum* species have been recommended for the treatment of various diseases [4, 5]. It is commonly used in the treatment of upper respiratory tract infection, diarrhoea, fever and conjunctivitis [6]. Recently, its hypoglycemic efficacy [7, 8] and safety [9] have been reported. It has also been revealed that it may have anti – haemorrhagic [10], antihypertensive, antimicrobial, psychostimulant effects [11]. The leaves of *O. gratissimum* contain a great quantity of thymol oil which has been regarded as highly antiseptic agent hence, its use by most people as mosquito repellent [12]. The juice of the fresh leaves is used as eye drops and is said to be a quick cure for conjunctivitis [13]. Its major constituents include aromatic and volatile oil, linolenic acid, oleic

acid, alkaloid, flavonoid, saponin and cardiac glycosides [14, 15]. The exact components of basil oil vary widely, being affected not only by these chemotypes but also by factors such as the time of day of harvest [16].

To avoid the side effects by administration of western medicines, growing studies of *Ocimum* species were performed to investigate their therapeutic potentials considering the wide range of diseases claimed to be treated by the plant. Thus, this study was designed to evaluate the chemical composition of *Ocimum gratissimum* and ascertain its efficacy and possible use as nutraceutical in health and disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection and preparation

Ocimum gratissimum leaves were identified and authenticated by a taxonomist of the Department of Botany, University of Calabar and a specimen copy was deposited in Department of Botany, University of Calabar, Nigeria. Five hundred grammes (500 g) of the fresh leaves were harvested and properly washed in tap water and then rinsed in distilled water to remove debris. The leaves were cut into small pieces and air-dried at room temperature (27 ± 1.50 °C) for seven days for phytochemicals investigation and for the determination of mineral elements. The samples were ground into powder and stored each in an air tight bottle prior to use for

analysis. Fresh leaf samples were used for the analysis of proximate composition and vitamins.

Phytochemical Analysis

Phytochemical analysis for tannins, polyphenols, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and Hydrocyanic acid content were carried out according to known and standard methods. Tannins were estimated using the Folin-Denis spectrophotometric method [17]. Saponin content was determined using the method of [18] as modified by [19]. Flavonoids and alkaloids were determined by ethyl acetate extraction and gravimetric measurement and the alkaline precipitation and gravimetric method respectively as described by [20]. Hydrocyanic acid content was determined using the alkaline titration method of [21].

Vitamin Analysis

The composition of the water-insoluble vitamins, riboflavin, thiamine and niacin, were determined by the method described by [22], while ascorbic acid content was determined by the method of [23]. Vitamin A concentration was determined by the spectrophotometric method described by [17]. Vitamin E was determined by the Fütter Mayer colorimetric method of the Association of Vitamin Chemist [24].

Mineral Analysis

Minerals were determined after the dried powdered samples were first digested with nitric acid and perchloric acid and the filtered aliquots were used for the determination of magnesium, iron, copper, zinc, selenium, chromium and manganese content. magnesium, iron, copper, zinc, selenium, chromium and manganese were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometric method described by [25] and [21].

Proximate Analysis

The analysis of the proximate composition of *O. gratissimum* leaf was carried out using the official methods of analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists [26] and the [27].

Determination of % Ash Content of *O. gratissimum*

Five grammes (5 g) of the leaf sample (fine form) was weighed into a porcelain dish that had previously been weighed. This was dried at 105 °C for three hours in an oven. The dish with content was transferred to a muffle furnace (Heraeus M 110) and ignited at 500 °C until free from carbon (residue appears greyish-white). This was removed from the oven and the ash moistened with a few drops of water (to expose bits of unashed carbon). The ash was re-dried in the oven at 100 °C for 3 hours and re-ashed in the furnace at 500 °C for another one hour. This was removed from the muffle furnace, placed in a desiccator until it cooled, and was then weighed.

The percentage ash was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{(Y-Z) \times 100}{X}$$

where,

X = sample weight prior to drying

Y = weight of dish and contents after ashing

Z = weight of empty dish.

Determination of % Crude Protein of *O. gratissimum*

Two grammes (2 g) of oven dried ground leaf sample was placed into 30 ml Kjeldahl digestion flask (Gerhardt). Fifteen millilitres (15 ml) of concentrated sulphuric acid and 1 g of catalyst mixture were added into the flask. The flask was gently heated on a digestion rack in a fume cupboard until a greenish clear solution appeared. After about 30 minutes when the digest had cleared, the flask was heated for another 30 minutes and allowed to cool. Ten millilitres (10 ml) of distilled water was added to avoid caking.

The sample was transferred to the Kjeldahl apparatus (Gerhardt). A 50 ml receiver flask containing 5 ml boric acid-indicator solution was placed under the condenser of the distillation apparatus so that the tip was about 2 cm inside the solution. To the digested sample in the apparatus was added 10 ml of 40% NaOH solution through funnel stopcock. Distillation commenced immediately by closing the steam by-pass and opening the inlet stopcock on the steam jet arm of the distillation apparatus. When the distillate reached the 35 ml mark on the receiver flask, distillation was stopped by closing inlet stopcock first, then opening the steam by-pass. The condenser tip was rinsed with distilled water. The excess acid was titrated to first pink colour with 0.1N NaOH.

The percentage crude protein was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Crude protein} = \frac{\text{Titre} \times 14.01 \times \text{Normality of the acid} \times 100 \times 6.25}{1000 \text{ weight of sample}}$$

Where, 6.25 is a general factor suitable for products in which the portion of specific protein is not well defined. 14.01/1000 is a constant and titre is the volume after titration.

Determination of % Crude Fat (Ether Extract) Content of *O. gratissimum*

Five grammes (5 g) of the ground leaf sample was placed in a thimble lined with a circle of filter paper. The thimble with its contents was placed in a 50 ml beaker and dried in an oven for 6 hours at 105 °C. The thimble with its contents was transferred to a Soxhlet extractor. The beaker was rinsed three times with ethyl ether and emptied into the Soxhlet extraction flask. The sample contained in the thimble was extracted with ethyl ether for 6 to 8 hours at a condensation rate of 3 - 6 drops per second. At the completion of the extraction, the fat extract was transferred from the extraction flask into a pre-weighed evaporating dish with several rinsing of ethyl ether. The evaporating dish was placed in a fumehood with the fan on, to evaporate the ethyl ether until no odour was detectable. The dish with its contents was dried in an oven for 30 minutes at 105 °C, removed from the oven, cooled in a desiccator to constant weight and weighed.

The percentage crude fat was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Crude fat ether extract} = \frac{W_2 - W_1 \times 100}{S}$$

where:

W1 = weight of empty evaporating dish

W2 = weight of evaporating dish + content after drying.

S = sample weight before drying.

Determination of % Crude Fibre Content of *O. gratissimum*

Five grammes (5 g) of ground sample was weighed and placed in a 1 litre conical flask. A 150 ml pre-heated 0.128 M H₂SO₄ was added and the content boiled for 30 minutes. The content was filtered through fluted funnel and the residue washed three times with hot water. To the digest was added 150 ml preheated 0.15 M KOH and heated to boiling. Some drops of antifoaming agent (n-octanol) was added and the content boiled slowly for 30 minutes, filtered and the residue washed three times with hot water, followed by washing three times with acetone in Cold Extraction Unit (Tecator 1615). The resulting residue was dried in the oven at 130 °C for 1 hr, cooled in a desiccator and weighed, and then ashed at 500 °C for 30 minutes, cooled in a desiccator and later weighed. The percentage crude fibre was calculated as follows:

where:

$$\% \text{ crude fibre} = \frac{W_2 - W_1 \times 100}{S}$$

W1

W1 = Sample weight before drying

W2 = Weight of residue after drying

W3 = Weight of residue after ashing

Statistical Analysis

All determinations were done in triplicates and data were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. These data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS

The results of the phytochemical composition, proximate analysis, mineral elements and vitamin composition of *O. gratissimum* are shown in Tables 1-4

Phytochemical Composition

Table 1 shows the types and quantities of secondary compounds of metabolism present in the leaf sample analyzed. Flavonoids were observed to have the highest value, followed by saponins and polyphenols. Thus, suggesting that *O. gratissimum* is a highly potent antioxidative plant.

Table 1. Phytochemical composition of *O. gratissimum* leaves (% W/W DMB)

Constituent	Mean \pm SEM
Tannins	0.56 \pm 0.04
Flavonoids	1.93 \pm 0.09
Alkaloids	0.41 \pm 0.01
Polyphenols	0.47 \pm 0.02
Saponins	1.06 \pm 0.03
Hydrocyanide	0.00 \pm 0.00

Values are mean \pm SEM of three determinations. *DMB = dry matter basis.

Proximate Composition

Table 2 shows the proximate composition *O. gratissimum* leaf sample. The crude fibre value was highest, followed by total protein, total fat and ash content. These results suggest the high nutritive value of the leaves.

Table 2. Proximate composition of Fresh leaves of *O. gratissimum* (mg/100 g)

Constituent	Mean \pm SEM
Total Protein	4.43 \pm 0.19
Total Fat	2.7 \pm 0.05
Crude Fibre	4.2 \pm 0.32
Ash Content	1.15 \pm 0.05

Values are mean \pm SEM of three determinations.

Mineral Profile

Presented on table 3 is the mineral composition of *O. gratissimum* plant sample. The value for Iron was the highest. Zinc, Copper, Chromium, Magnesium, Manganese and Selenium were present in appreciable quantities. Hence, confirming the rich mineral composition of the plant and validating its use in ethno-medicine.

Table 3. Mineral Composition of fresh leaves of *O. gratissimum* (%W/W DMB)

Constituent	Mean \pm SEM
Fe	7.03 \pm 0.19
Zn	0.004 \pm 0.89
Cu	0.01 \pm 0.12
Cr	-
Mg	0.06 \pm 0.58

Mn 0.002 \pm 0.02

Se 0.36 \pm 0.07

Values are mean \pm SEM of three determinations.

Vitamin Composition

Table 4 shows the results of the vitamin composition of the leaf sample of *O. gratissimum*. The presence of vitamins A, C, E, riboflavin, niacin and thiamine supports the high antioxidant value of the plant.

Table 4. Vitamin Composition of fresh leaves of *O. gratissimum* (mg/100 g and %)

Constituent	Mean \pm SEM
Vitamin A	1402.33 \pm 5.89IU/100g
Vitamin C	0.0025 \pm 0.36 mg/100g
Vitamin E	19.33 \pm 0.88 mg/100g
Riboflavin	7.8 \pm 0.06%
Niacin	4.11 \pm 0.11%
Thiamine	23.33 \pm 1.2%

Values are mean \pm SEM of three determinations.

DISCUSSION

The phytochemical screening of the *O. gratissimum* leaves revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoid and saponin. The presence of these phytochemicals in the investigated plant account for its usefulness as medicinal plants. Flavonoids were observed to have the highest value, followed by saponins and polyphenols. Flavonoids have several proven medicinal properties, such as their ability to strengthen veins and to decrease their permeability. They also have anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, antibacterial and antiviral properties [28]. Flavonoids are potent water soluble antioxidants and free radical scavengers which prevent oxidative cell damage, and have strong anticancer and anti-ulcer activity and protection against the different levels of carcinogenesis [29].

Saponin may be steroidal or triterpenoids. The occurrence of steroidal saponins in *O. gratissimum* and from various studies indicate their importance and interest in pharmacy due to their relationship with such compounds such as sex hormones especially in development of the female contraceptive pill [29]. In another work, saponin was stated to be a potential remedy for the management of atherosclerosis and other related disorders like diabetes and obesity [30]. According to [31], saponin has been demonstrated to affect nutrient uptake through the intestinal mucosal cells in vitro, inhibiting active mucosal transport and facilitating uptake of substances that are normally not absorbed.

Polyphenols is a type of antioxidant containing a polyphenolic or natural phenol substructure. Consuming dietary polyphenols from *O. gratissimum* may be associated with possible reduction in inflammation such as in coronary artery disease [32]. Polyphenols may also play a role in preventing degenerative diseases, particularly cardiovascular diseases, cancers and osteoporosis as well as prevention of neurodegenerative diseases and diabetes mellitus [33].

There was an appreciable amount of tannins in the leaf being studied. Tannins have been shown to be anticarcinogenic and antimutagenic, these properties may be related to their antioxidative property, which is important in protecting cellular oxidative damage including lipid peroxidation [34]. The antimicrobial activities of tannins are well documented. Tannins have been reported to also accelerate blood clotting, reduces blood pressure, decrease serum lipid profile and modulate immunoresponses [35]. Alkaloids were present in the leaves of *O.*

gratissimum. Several alkaloid containing medicinal plants are reported to have been used by the early man as analgesic (pain relievers), as recreational stimulants [36]. They also possess antimalarial, cardiac antiarrhythmic, anticancer and antihypertensive properties [37, 38].

The protein value was highest for the proximate composition of the leaves. Thus, indicating that the leaves of *O. gratissimum* as a potent body building food for maintenance and repairs of worn out tissues and for the supply of energy and adequate amount of required amino acids [39]. The leaves are also a very rich source of crude fiber. Fibre reduces the risk of developing heart diseases, diabetes, diverticular disease and constipation. It has a physiological effect on the gastrointestinal function of promoting the reduction of tracolonic pressure which is beneficial in diverticular disease. Fibre also has a biochemical effect on the absorption and re-absorption of bile acids and consequently the absorption of dietary fats and cholesterol [40]. Fats were detected in the leaves although not in high amount as compared to protein and fiber. Fats are beneficial to the health because it serves as energy storage, breakdown of fat soluble vitamins and phytonutrients and hormone synthesis. Despite its numerous benefits, high fat diet may be implicated in weight gain and subsequent development of various cardiovascular diseases, hence the importance of limiting its consumption. The low fat amount in the leaf is promissory in body weight control, control of blood cholesterol, obesity and reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases [41].

Micronutrient vitamins and minerals were demonstrated in this study. Iron and Selenium are the most abundant minerals observed in the leaves. Chromium was not detected, while other minerals were present in trace quantities. The study also reveals the presence of vitamins A, C, E, thiamine, niacin and riboflavin. Vitamin A was more significant.

CONCLUSION

The findings from this work therefore indicate that the leaves extract of *O. gratissimum*, may be a good source of medically active phytochemicals and micronutrients relevant in nutrition and drug formulation with the potential of ameliorating a wide range of diseases, including diabetes, malarial and cardiovascular problems.

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